

Cognitive Learning Biases Among Qassim University Students And Its Relationship With Their Major And Academic Achievement Level

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Abstract

To take a decision is an important issue in our daily life in general and in learning in specific. When individuals take decisions they resort to their experience and previous knowledge. The aim of this study was to investigate Qassim University student's learning cognitive biases. Students registered for the second semester 2020/ 2021 (No. 256) participated in the study. The researcher implemented "Davos Assessment of Cognitive Biases" scale, Arabized by Al-Hammouri (2017); the scale measures seven domains. The results revealed a moderate level of cognitive biases among the students in the domains measured and overall scale. Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the major effect on all the domains were found in favor of humanitarian majoring students; and on academic level in favor of low academic achievers; as well as on the interaction between major and academic level in the domains of Jumping to conclusions, social cognition problems, and safety behaviors.

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Introduction

The human mind is often hindered from seeing things fairly; cognitive bias is one of the hindrances that occur while acquiring knowledge. Therefore, cognitive bias as a concept describes incorrect mental performance that leads to inaccurate decision making and perceptions distortion.

Ogdeh (1999) defined cognitive biases as thinking tendency at times to systematic deviations in rationality levels or rational judgments. Van der Gaag and his research team (2013) defined it as cognitive mistakes committed as a result of mental inference processes incorrect practices which hinder individuals correct thinking. Randall (2012) said cognitive biases refer to hypothesis build on incomplete information. In a similar respect Gardenier and Resnik (2002) identified cognitive biases as the distance from clarity in information gathering, analyzing, interpreting and presenting in an incorrect manner.

The term of cognitive bias is a general term that is used to describe the performance of the human mind, deviations that lead to distortion of cognition, such deviations usually occur because we attempt to simplify the information to comply with the experiences and knowledge we have, or knows nothing other than it, or we are not willing to know another thing that contradicts with what we know. (Haselton & Nettle, 2006)

Scholars provided many explanations of cognitive bias. For instance, the information processing method believes that cognitive biases occur in information collecting, processing and output. Cognitive bias correlates with information processing by the way of caring for certain types of information (Hogarth & Makridakis, 1981). In the cognitive bias the information processing diverts a lot in the assessing information, and judging stimulus which in turn leads into cognitive distortion and illogical explanations or what is termed as irrationality. (Van der Gaag et al., 2013)

While Kahneman and Tversky (1974) believe that cognitive bias in information processing occurs while intuition-dependent decisions are taken, or when more than one decision by using inaccurate observation, or visual bias that relies on narrow vision. These types of cognitive biases are not necessarily passive, according to psychologists information processing and judgments might be effective if personal adjustment is sought. Cognitive bias is not restricted to normal individuals only; professional researchers are exposed to cognitive bias when they think intuitively. (Piatelli-Palmarin, 1994)

Other scholars (Chan, Ho, Law & Pau, 2013) believe that psychopaths fail to recognize safety information; instead they focus on processing threatening related information. Everaert and his research team (2016) confirmed that psychopaths focus on passive events more than focusing on the positive events; psychopaths bring about passive conclusions and explanations for the emotive information more than the positives. This is correlated with the reasons of the emotional passive state, to its explanations and conclusions rather than

considering positive meanings and explanations, this state discriminates adjusted and maladjusted individuals with the surrounding environment and its events.

Cognitive biases may be explained by the existence of two or more contradicted ideas that generate a powerful desire to decrease the contradiction or psychological agitation between the two ideas to transfer from distress into psychological ease. (Mathews & MacLeod, 2002)

Another explanation associate bias with expectations, the human mind tend to be biased, that means individuals tend to what supports their expectations and beliefs, so they tend to adopt beliefs that supports their needs and desires. The theory of expectations revolves on cognitive mental processes whereas individuals narrow their choices through the expected result; this fact explains the selection of a certain behavioral situation or a certain decision to receive the sought result. (Fromm, 1989)

Van der Gaag and his team (2013) confirmed that cognitive biases include; selective attention which means focusing on certain thing in the surrounding environment for a specific time while ignoring other stimulus, inferential bias known as jumping to conclusions which transfers complex tasks into simple tasks or processes, this type is useful in general but sometimes it leads to huge and systematic mistakes, belief inflexibility which hinders individuals' proper thinking, associative bias which correlates with the tendency to reduce the potential coincidence and exaggerate the potential causality between things and events, and source control bias which is represented by the individuals' attribution of his ideas and emotional state to external sources.

While Goldstein (2015) classifies the inferential process errors sources into eight types: availability, in which the individual gives increased occurrence potential for the easily recalled events, illusory correlation which refers to the illusion of a strong relation between two events although the correlation does not exist, representativeness which refers to the individuals belief that there is a potential that one of the events is a part of another event based on the degree of similarity between the two events. The rate base refers to the potential of increasing the rate of certain events based on the offered description rather than the percentage of its existence in the society. Conjunction rule means the giving a potential occurrence rate of two events together rather than separate occurrence. Law of large numbers refers to judgments based on unrepresentative samples of the society. Bias confirmation refers to individuals search for information that supports his hypothesis and ignoring what reputes it. Myside bias is a type of confirmation bias, it refers to individuals generating evidence and evaluating them, testing hypothesis to consistent with his point of view and direction. Some factors influence cognitive bias such as: framing which influences decisions and judgments and renders them inaccurate and far away from knowledge (Jensen, 1966). Anchoring effect occurs when a person gives value and importance in attention to a situation than other situations and it leads to inaccurate incorrect results (Schkade & Kahneman, 1998). Halo effect occurs when previous impressions about an event emerge and are influenced with bias thinking in decision making. (Al-Obeidi, 2009)

The researcher believes that cognitive biases are closely correlated with several processes that are not often differentiated, cognitive biases influence attention, decision making, memory processes and information retrieval. Cognitive biases occur because of the human cognitive ability restrictions to assimilate and process the available information in a correct manner and leads to biased decisions as a result of personal cognitive factors or external factors.

Scholars build their cognitive bias research on different aspects; many research confirmed the causative relation between the factors of cognitive bias on one side and specific psychological disorders such as anxiety, depression and social phobia as the study of Mathews and MacLeod (2005) mentioned. In a similar aspect children's behaviours are examined for cognitive bias, and to find out their opinions about everyday life as the study of Suarez and Bell-Dolan (2001) revealed.

Few studies attempted to train people to control attention and direct it away from negative stimulus, or to train people on positive stimulus explanations, such as Hakamata et al. (2010). Al-Alwani and Al-Atoum (2019) aimed to decrease cognitive biases using metacognitive thinking skills. Jabr and Enad (2020) examined the correlation between motivation and learning among postgraduates. On a similar aspect, Aziz and Saleh (2019) examined the correlation between cognitive bias and student's ambition.

Few studies intersected with the current study variables. For instance Jaber and Abed Al-Ameer (2017) studied university students cognitive bias, 500 randomly selected postgraduates from Al-Qadisiyah University participated in the study; their majors were scientific and humanitarian. The researchers used the Arabic version of Fromm (1964) test; it has 41 items distributed on four categories: irrational ideas, personal self-expectations, perceptual distortions, and psychological disability. The results indicated that the cognitive bias is insignificant; no differences were found attributed to the student's majors.

Al-Hammouri (2017) studied cognitive bias among a sample of Yarmouk university postgraduates (No. =496) and tested them using the Arabic version of DACOBS. A moderate level of cognitive biases was found, attention to threats ranked first followed by jumping to conclusions and the last rank was for safety behaviours. Results also showed that cognitive biases related to external attribution was higher among male students compared to female students; it was also found that low academic achievers have higher levels of cognitive bias compared with high achievers. Mahmoud and Al-Lami (2020) examined the significance of cognitive bias

among kindergarten department female postgraduates (No.=400) enrolled in 1st, 2nd, 3rd, and 4th years. It was found that students have cognitive bias but differences between different levels were not found.

The previous literature indicate that cognitive bias caught researchers attention, and they tried to explain the reasons for cognitive bias and its relation with many fields, how to measure it and reduce it. The current study differs from previous literature by its variables, the study attempted to examine cognitive bias among Qassim University students according to student's major and academic achievement.

Study Questions

Cognitive bias correlates with few processes, sometimes it is hard to differentiate between them. Cognitive bias influence attention, decision making, judgments, causal relations, memory processes and information retrieval (Van der Gaag et al., 2013). Cognitive bias affects individual's mental health and their ability to process environmental stimulus efficiently (Chan, Ho, Law & Pau, 2013). Many studies proved that cognitive bias may be measured (Bastiaens et al., 2013), and may be adjusted (Hakamata et al., 2010). The current study will attempt to examine the level of cognitive bias found among Qassim University students and how it differs according to the student major and academic achievement level.

Assuming a correlation between cognitive biases on one hand and students major and academic achievement is possible. Cognitive biases are very important in the educational process, it reflects to a large extent the individual differences between learners, and it helps educators to explain the change in the learners' academic achievement according to the students major. Cognitive biases as the researcher believes is considered of the restrictions that affect learners output, therefore the researcher attempted to understand this correlation.

In specific the researcher attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of cognitive biases among Qassim university students?
2. Are there any statistical differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) in cognitive biases among Qassim university students attributed to major, academic achievement and their interaction?

Study Importance

Theoretically the study tests the validity of DCOBS test in measuring cognitive biases of Qassim university students, because as far as the researcher can tell, the current study is the first attempt to examine and measure cognitive biases at the local level, to find the differences attributed to the students major and academic achievement, and to examine the causal relationship which has not been examined before.

Empirically, the study is hoped to offer mental health and psychological counselors a universal codified tool that is reliable for the local environment. The test constructed may help to reveal cognitive biases that have an effect in many psychological disorders, and the potential adjustment through cognitive behavioral therapy programs. It is expected to open new horizons for local mental health and psychological specialists to study the cognitive biases relationship with student's disorders.

Study Limitations

Generalizing the results of the study may be hindered by the following: first. The sample selected, the test was implemented on a sample selected by availability of enrolled students in the second semester of the academic year 2020/ 2021 at Qassim University. Second. The specificity of the cognitive bias test implemented (DCOBS) and measurement of seven specific variables.

Procedural Definitions

Cognitive biases are mistakes committed by the individual as a result of incorrect practices of mental inferences processes. It is defined procedurally by the degree obtained by answering DCOBS test items.

Academic achievement is the cognitive outcome acquired at the university, it is measured by the students obtained marks and averages (excellent, very good, good, and accepted) at Qassim university.

Major. The students major in the postgraduate stage (humanitarian, scientific).

Methodology

The researcher employed a descriptive-retrospective methodology to examine the effect of major and academic achievement level on the student's cognitive bias at Qassim University.

Study Population Sampling

The study population included all the postgraduates enrolled in the second semester of the academic year 2020/ 2021, overall number 2199 postgraduate. The sample selection implemented the convenient method sampling from humanitarian and scientific faculties, the overall number of the participants was 256 postgraduate, and the sample description is illustrated in table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of the Sample

	Categories	Freq.	Percent
Major	Scientific	108	42.2
	Humanitarian	148	57.8
	Excellent	27	10.5
Academic Level	Very good	49	19.1
	Good	112	43.8
	Accepted	68	26.6

Study Variables

The study involved three variables major (scientific and humanitarian), level of academic achievement (Excellent, very good, good, and accepted), and cognitive bias.

The Study Instrument

The study utilized Davos Assessment of Cognitive Biases Scale (DCOBS), the scale was developed by Van der Gaag et al. (2013), it included 42 items, the students completed the test according to their level of certainty on a 7-point likert type scale ranging from (strongly disagree, disagree, somewhat disagree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat agree, agree, and strongly agree), the scale includes three key dimensions and sub-dimensions.

First: Cognitive Biases

The scale measures: jumping into conclusions, means the bias in collecting information and conclusions, it is measured by items (3, 8, 16, 18, 25, 30); belief inflexibility means the inflexibility of thinking and questioning various information and sources, it is measured by items (13, 15, 26, 34, 38, 41); attention to threats means focusing on a type of information or hypothesis and reducing the importance of other types or ignoring them, it is measured by items (1, 2, 6, 10, 20, 37); and external attribution which means the individuals attribution of ideas and emotiveness to external sources, it is measured by items (7, 12, 17, 22, 24, 29).

Second. Cognitive Restrictions

Human cognition is restricted by certain problems such as: social cognition problems means that is inability to understand others motives, ideas, and emotions, it is measured by items (4, 9, 11, 14, 19, 39); subjective cognition problems is the individual loss of focus while performing various tasks, it measured by items (5, 21, 28, 32, 36, 40);and safety behaviours is practicing avoidant behaviours to stay away from potential dangers, it is measured by items (23, 27, 31, 33, 35, 42).

DCOBS Validity and Reliability

Van der Gaag et al. (2013) insured the validity DCOBS test. They used the factorial analysis to find the explanatory variance, the seven domains of the test explained 45% of the overall variance of the test. Two methods are used to find the validity coefficient; discriminant validity was insured by testing a sample of psychopaths, they obtained higher degrees compared with a control group, convergent validity was insured by computing coefficients of 5 dimensions of DCOBS with a number of tests related to fluency and memory, the spearman rho scores range from (0.36 – 0.627).

Reliability was insured by calculating the internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's alpha), Split half reliability, and retested the students, the scores between each domain and overall score range was (0.64-0.90), (0.70-0.92), and (0.72-0.92).

Adapting DCOBS to Arab Environment

Al-Hammouri (2017) translated DCOBS scale into Arabic, and presented the translation to three translators to review the Arabic version, they provided comments and the researcher processed their comments. Ten reviewers majoring in educational psychology, counseling psychology, measurement and evaluation reviewed the scale for age suitability, language soundness, and item suitability. They commented on the language soundness and their observations were handled. The scale was administered on a pilot sample of 70 (30 male and 40 female) student, the internal consistency coefficient (Cronbach's alpha) was computed. Results proved the scale suitability to be used in his study. Cronbach's alpha overall values scored (0.87) and domains values scored (0.69-0.80).

Adapted DCOBS Reliability

To ensure the test suitability to the Arab environment it was administered on the pilot sample after an interval of three weeks, the consistency coefficient is computed, the results proved that Pearson correlation values of the two times were high and acceptable for the purpose of the study. Overall reliability of the scale value was (0.89) and for the dimensions, it ranged between (0.77-0.80).

Adapted DCOBS Validity for the purpose of the current study

Construct Validity

The researcher computed correlation coefficients between each items and the overall degree, and between each item and the domain that connects with it from the responses of a pilot sample composed of 30 students. The items correlation with the overall scores range (0.40-0.81) and with the domains the scores range (0.43-0.89) as illustrated in table 2.

Table 2. Correlation Coefficient between Item, Domain, and Scale

Item No.	Item-domain correlation coefficient	Item-scale correlation coefficient	Item No.	Item-domain correlation coefficients	Item-scale correlation coefficient	Item No.	Item-domain correlation coefficient	Item-scale correlation coefficient
1	0.62(**)	0.63(**)	15	0.84(**)	0.68(**)	29	0.87(**)	0.73(**)
2	0.55(**)	0.43(*)	16	0.80(**)	0.66(**)	30	0.64(**)	0.61(**)

Table 2. Correlation Coefficient between Item, Domain, and Scale

Item No.	Item-domain correlation coefficient	Item-scale correlation coefficient	Item No.	Item-domain correlation coefficients	Item-scale correlation coefficient	Item No.	Item-domain correlation coefficient	Item-scale correlation coefficient
3	0.62(**)	0.62(**)	17	0.75(**)	0.66(**)	31	0.59(**)	0.65(**)
4	0.79(**)	0.67(**)	18	0.73(**)	0.71(**)	32	0.43(*)	0.60(**)
5	0.45(*)	0.62(**)	19	0.62(**)	0.58(**)	33	0.74(**)	0.63(**)
6	0.80(**)	0.55(**)	20	0.45(*)	0.87(**)	34	0.81(**)	0.81(**)
7	0.78(**)	0.72(**)	21	0.49(**)	0.48(**)	35	0.88(**)	0.79(**)
8	0.71(**)	0.71(**)	22	0.84(**)	0.70(**)	36	0.83(**)	0.72(**)
9	0.73(**)	0.66(**)	23	0.84(**)	0.68(**)	37	0.61(**)	0.42(*)
10	0.71(**)	0.67(**)	24	0.66(**)	0.67(**)	38	0.81(**)	0.42(*)
11	0.65(**)	0.68(**)	25	0.71(**)	0.55(**)	39	0.79(**)	0.72(**)
12	0.71(**)	0.58(**)	26	0.85(**)	0.65(**)	40	0.83(**)	0.50(**)
13	0.77(**)	0.68(**)	27	0.78(**)	0.72(**)	41	0.57(**)	0.41(*)
14	0.77(**)	0.52(**)	28	0.89(**)	0.71(**)	42	0.54(**)	0.40(*)

* significant at 0.05

** significant at 0.01

As observed in table 2, all the correlation coefficients were acceptable and significant; therefore, none of the items was deleted.

Correlation coefficients between the domain with the overall scale degree and between the domains are computed as table 3 illustrate.

Table 3. Correlation Coefficients between the Domains and Overall Degree

	Jumping to conclusion	Belief inflexibility	Attention for threats	External attribution	social cognition problems	Subjective cognition problems	Safety behaviors	Overall
Jumping to conclusion	1							
Belief inflexibility	0.725(**)	1						
Attention for threats	0.498(**)	0.618(**)	1					
External attribution	0.459(*)	0.721(**)	0.801(**)	1				
social cognition problems	0.557(**)	0.779(**)	0.466(**)	0.700(**)	1			
Subjective cognition problems	0.545(**)	0.857(**)	0.652(**)	0.681(**)	0.674(**)	1		
Safety behaviors	0.444(*)	0.481(**)	0.232	0.237	0.321	0.314	1	
Overall	0.732(**)	0.938(**)	0.781(**)	0.855(**)	0.828(**)	0.861(**)	0.519(**)	1

* significant at 0.05

** significant at 0.01

As table 3 showed all the correlation coefficients are acceptable and significant, this result refers to an acceptable degree of construct validity.

DCOBS Stability

The instrument stability was insured through testing the pilot sample and retesting them after an interval of two weeks, and Pearson Correlation coefficient is computed between the estimates of the responses in the two times. Internal consistency is insured by calculating Cronbach's Alpha coefficients. Table 4 shows internal consistency and the retest results of the domains and overall scale, the overall scale scored (88.0) and the domains scores range (75.0-84.0), these scores are considered appropriate for the purpose of the current result.

Table 4. Internal Consistency and Test re-Test Reliability of the Domains and Overall Degree

Domain	Test re-test reliability	Internal consistency
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Jumping to conclusion	0.92	0.81
Belief inflexibility	0.89	0.79
Attention for threats	0.88	0.84
External attribution	0.91	0.80
social cognition problems	0.87	0.77
Subjective cognition problems	0.93	0.75
Safety behaviors	0.89	0.79
Overall degree	0.92	0.88

DCOBS Correction

The participants completed the test (42 items) according to their level of certainty on a 7-point Likert type scale ranging from (strongly agree, agree, somewhat agree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree), each response is given degrees (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7) respectively, hence, the lowest degree obtained is 7 and the highest is 42, while the highest degree for each domain is 42 and for the scale as a whole is 294. All items directions were positive. DCOBS Cut-off Degrees

A 7-point Likert type scale type was adopted in the study, the answers rang from (strongly agree, agree, somewhat agree, neither agree nor disagree, somewhat disagree, disagree, and strongly disagree), each selection receives a score (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7), scores from 1.00-3.00 is considered low, 3.01-5.00 is moderate and 5.01-7.00 is high...etc. The following formula is used to compute the results:

$$\frac{\text{highest score (7)} - \text{lowest score (1)}}{\text{number of the categories}} \times \frac{7-1}{3} = 2.00, \text{ the sum is added to the end of each category.}$$

Results

The study answered the first question of "What is the level of cognitive biases among Qassim university students?" by calculating means and standard deviations of the cognitive bias level as seen in table 5.

Table 5. Means and Standard Deviations of Cognitive Bias by Means Scores in a Descending Order

Rank	#	Domain	M.	Std.	Level
1	5	Social cognition problems	4.02	0.648	Moderate
2	4	External attribution	4.00	0.771	Moderate
3	6	Subjective cognition problems	3.98	0.591	Moderate
4	2	Belief inflexibility	3.58	0.927	Moderate
5	3	Attention for threats	3.51	0.702	Moderate
6	1	Jumping to conclusion	3.24	0.525	Moderate
7	7	Safety behaviors	3.17	0.550	Moderate
		Overall	3.64	0.542	Moderate

As table 5 illustrate, means score range (3.17-4.02), the highest means score was for social cognition problems (M. = 4.02), external attribution ranked second (M. = 4.00), subjective cognition problems followed (M. = 3.98), safety behaviors ranked last (M. = 3.17). The overall means score was (M. = 3.64).

To answer the second question of "Are there any statistical differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) in cognitive biases among Qassim university students attributed to major, academic achievement and their interaction?", the researcher calculated the means and standard deviations of the students cognitive biases based on major and academic achievement level as table 6 illustrate.

Table 6. Cognitive Bias Means and Standard Deviations According to Major and Academic Achievement Level

Domains	Academic achievement level	Scientific			Humanitarian			Overall		
		M.	Std.	No.	M.	Std.	No.	M.	Std.	No.
Jumping to conclusion	Excellent	2.64	0.324	12	2.69	0.372	15	2.67	0.346	27
	Very good	2.79	0.190	14	2.92	0.344	35	2.88	0.312	49
	Good	3.01	0.366	46	3.43	0.455	66	3.26	0.467	112
	Accepted	3.71	0.353	36	3.71	0.352	32	3.71	0.350	68
	Overall	3.17	0.521	108	3.29	0.524	148	3.24	0.525	256
Belief inflexibility	Excellent	1.83	0.369	12	2.50	0.504	15	2.20	0.555	27
	Very good	2.32	0.400	14	3.11	0.414	35	2.89	0.544	49

		Good	3.17	0.437	46	4.10	0.531	66	3.72	0.675	112
		Accepted	3.99	0.348	36	4.87	0.436	32	4.40	0.592	68
		Overall	3.18	0.820	108	3.87	0.894	148	3.58	0.927	256
		Excellent	2.50	0.590	12	2.58	0.301	15	2.54	0.445	27
		Very good	2.92	0.351	14	3.19	0.539	35	3.11	0.504	49
Attention	for	Good	3.36	0.546	46	3.74	0.496	66	3.58	0.548	112
threats		Accepted	3.81	0.588	36	4.33	0.384	32	4.05	0.563	68
		Overall	3.35	0.683	108	3.62	0.698	148	3.51	0.702	256
External		Excellent	2.61	0.179	12	2.96	0.271	15	2.80	0.289	27
attribution		Very good	3.00	0.358	14	3.77	0.480	35	3.55	0.567	49
		Good	3.86	0.604	46	4.35	0.557	66	4.15	0.623	112
		Accepted	4.45	0.592	36	4.68	0.426	32	4.56	0.530	68
		Overall	3.81	0.820	108	4.14	0.703	148	4.00	0.771	256
		Excellent	2.85	0.505	12	3.46	0.486	15	3.19	0.574	27
Social		Very good	3.01	0.474	14	3.81	0.388	35	3.58	0.548	49
cognition		Good	3.74	0.497	46	4.43	0.381	66	4.15	0.549	112
problems		Accepted	4.36	0.336	36	4.59	0.261	32	4.47	0.323	68
		Overall	3.75	0.693	108	4.22	0.535	148	4.02	0.648	256
		Excellent	2.93	0.399	12	3.24	0.436	15	3.10	0.441	27
Subjective		Very good	3.25	0.351	14	3.80	0.357	35	3.64	0.431	49
cognition		Good	3.83	0.407	46	4.36	0.444	66	4.14	0.499	112
problems		Accepted	4.18	0.411	36	4.45	0.350	32	4.31	0.404	68
		Overall	3.77	0.573	108	4.13	0.559	148	3.98	0.591	256
Safety		Excellent	2.21	0.176	12	2.82	0.375	15	2.55	0.431	27
behaviours		Very good	2.56	0.304	14	3.09	0.477	35	2.94	0.495	49
		Good	3.05	0.454	46	3.36	0.453	66	3.23	0.475	112
		Accepted	3.18	0.347	36	3.85	0.299	32	3.50	0.470	68
		Overall	2.94	0.494	108	3.35	0.525	148	3.17	0.550	256
Overall		Excellent	2.51	0.162	12	2.89	0.220	15	2.72	0.273	27
		Very good	2.84	0.154	14	3.38	0.229	35	3.23	0.326	49
		Good	3.43	0.223	46	3.97	0.250	66	3.75	0.356	112
		Accepted	3.95	0.163	36	4.35	0.142	32	4.14	0.253	68
		Overall	3.43	0.518	108	3.80	0.504	148	3.64	0.542	256

Table 6 showed an apparent discrepancy in the means and standard deviations of the student's cognitive biases attributed to the difference of major and academic achievement level. To determine the functionality of the differences, the researcher used Two-way MANOVA analysis to analyze the domains results and ANOVA analysis on the overall scale.

Table 7. Two-Way MANOVA Analysis of the Major and Academic Achievement Level and their Interaction Effect on Cognitive Biases Domains

Source of variance	Domains	Sum Squares	of	Degree of freedom	Means square	f-Value	Sign.
Major Hotelling's Trace= 1.385 H=0.000	Jumping to conclusion	1.047		1	1.047	7.367	0.007
	Belief inflexibility	31.153		1	31.153	154.436	0.000
	Attention for threats	4.496		1	4.496	17.781	0.000
	External attribution	9.749		1	9.749	36.962	0.000
	Social cognition problems	15.689		1	15.689	95.512	0.000
	Subjective cognition problems	7.863		1	7.863	48.356	0.000
	Safety behaviors	13.051		1	13.051	79.249	0.000
Academic achievement Wilks' Lambda=0.135 H=0.000	Jumping to conclusion	29.760		3	9.920	69.810	0.000
	Belief inflexibility	132.025		3	44.008	218.163	0.000
	Attention for threats	54.873		3	18.291	72.342	0.000
	External attribution	77.151		3	25.717	97.508	0.000

Table 7. Two-Way MANOVA Analysis of the Major and Academic Achievement Level and their Interaction Effect on Cognitive Biases Domains

Source of variance	Domains	Sum of Squares	Degree of freedom	Means square	f-Value	Sign.
Major academic achievement Wilks' Lambda=0.779 H=0.000	Socialcognition problems	48.987	3	16.329	99.411	0.000
	Subjective cognition problems	38.404	3	12.801	78.727	0.000
	Safety behaviors	24.326	3	8.109	49.237	0.000
	Jumping to conclusion	2.153	3	0.718	5.050	0.002
	Belief inflexibility	.453	3	0.151	0.749	0.524
	Attention for threats	1.046	3	0.349	1.379	0.250
	External attribution	1.941	3	0.647	2.453	0.064
	Socialcognition problems	2.863	3	0.954	5.810	0.001
	Subjective cognition problems	.904	3	0.301	1.852	0.138
	Safety behaviors	1.673	3	0.558	3.386	0.019
	Error	Jumping to conclusion	35.241	248	0.142	
Belief inflexibility		50.027	248	0.202		
Attention for threats		62.705	248	0.253		
External attribution		65.408	248	0.264		
Socialcognition problems		40.736	248	0.164		
Subjective cognition problems		40.326	248	0.163		
Safety behaviors		40.843	248	0.165		
Overall	Jumping to conclusion	70.320	255			
	Belief inflexibility	219.277	255			
	Attention for threats	125.767	255			
	External attribution	151.722	255			
	Socialcognition problems	107.082	255			
	Subjective cognition problems	89.090	255			
	Safety behaviors	77.070	255			

Table 7 showed the following:

- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the effect of major in favor of humanitarian majors are noticed in all the domains.
- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the effect of academic achievement are noticed in all the domains, to determine the functionality of the means differences Scheffé method is used as seen in table 8.
- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the effect of interaction between students major and academic achievement are noticed in the domains, except for “belief inflexibility, attention for threats, external attribution, and subjective cognition problems”, the means differences is represented in the figures 1, 2, 3.

Table 8. Two-way MANOVA Analysis of the Major and Academic Achievement Level Effect on Cognitive Bias

Source of variance	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Sum of squares	f-value	Sign.
Major	10.069	1	10.069	228.532	0.000
Academic level	52.953	3	17.651	400.609	0.000
Major*Academic level	.293	3	0.098	2.213	0.087
Error	10.927	248	0.044		
Overall	74.899	255			

Table eight illustrated:

- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the effect of major are observed, F-value scored 228.532 and a significance of 0.000.
- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the effect of academic achievement is observed, F-value scored 400.609 and a significance of 0.000, to determine the functionality of the means differences Scheffé method is used as seen in table 9.

- No significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the interaction between students major and academic achievement are found, F-value scored 2.213 and a significance of 0.087.

Table 9. Scheffé Comparisons of the Academic Achievement Level Effect on the Students Cognitive Bias

		M.	Excellent	Very good	Good	Accepted
Jumping to conclusion	Excellent	2.67				
	Very good	2.88	0.21			
	Good	3.26	0.59*	0.38*		
	Accepted	3.71	1.04*	0.83*	0.45*	
Belief inflexibility	Excellent	2.20				
	Very good	2.89	0.68*			
	Good	3.72	1.51*	0.83*		
	Accepted	4.40	2.20*	1.52*	0.69*	
Attention for threats	Excellent	2.54				
	Very good	3.11	0.57*			
	Good	3.58	1.04*	0.47*		
	Accepted	4.05	1.51*	0.95*	0.47*	
External attribution	Excellent	2.80				
	Very good	3.55	0.75*			
	Good	4.15	1.34*	0.59*		
	Accepted	4.56	1.76*	1.01*	0.41*	
Social cognition problems	Excellent	3.19				
	Very good	3.58	0.40*			
	Good	4.15	0.97*	0.57*		
	Accepted	4.47	1.28*	0.88*	0.32*	
Subjective cognition problems	Excellent	3.10				
	Very good	3.64	0.53*			
	Good	4.14	1.04*	0.50*		
	Accepted	4.31	1.20*	0.67*	0.17	
Safety behaviors	Excellent	2.55				
	Very good	2.94	0.39*			
	Good	3.23	0.68*	0.29*		
	Accepted	3.50	0.95*	0.56*	0.26*	
Overall degree	Excellent	2.72				
	Very good	3.23	0.50*			
	Good	3.75	1.02*	0.52*		
	Accepted	4.14	1.42*	0.92*	0.40*	

* significant at ($\alpha = 0.05$)

As seen in table 9:

- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) between good academic achievement and both of excellent and very good academic achievement levels, in favor of good academic achievement is apparent. Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) between accepted and excellent, very good and good academic achievement is observed in favor of accepted level in “jumping to conclusions”.

- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) between very good academic achievement and excellent academic achievement levels, in favor of very good academic achievement is apparent. Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) are found between accepted academic achievement and excellent, very good and good academic achievement levels in favor of accepted academic achievement in “belief inflexibility, attention for threats, external attribution, social cognition problems, safety behaviors” and overall degree.

- Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) between very good academic achievement and excellent academic achievement levels, in favor of very good academic achievement. Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) are found between accepted academic achievement and both of excellent and very good in favor of accepted academic achievement in the cognitive problems.

Figure 1. Interaction between major and academic achievement level in jumping to conclusions
As observed in figure 1 the interaction between major and academic achievement in jumping to conclusions was in favor of the humanitarian majors and in all academic achievement levels.

Figure 2. Interaction between major and academic achievement level in social cognition problems
As observed in figure 2 the interaction between major and academic achievement in social cognition problems was in favor of the humanitarian majors and in all academic achievement levels.

Figure 3. Interaction between major and academic achievement level in safety behaviours
As observed in figure 3 the interaction between major and academic achievement in safety behaviours was in favor of the humanitarian majors and in all academic achievement levels.

Discussion

The results revealed a moderate level of cognitive biases among Qassim University students. The social cognition problems ranked first and scored a means of ($M. = 4.02$); external attribution ranked second and scored a means of ($M= 4.00$); Subjective cognition problems ranked third and scored a means of ($M. = 3.98$); safety behaviors ranked fourth and scored a means of ($M. = 3.17$).

Results showed that few students have high cognitive biases; this result refers to a threat related to cognitive biases where an individual organizes his responses in everyday life events. Luecken, Tartaro and Appelhans (2004) said that guiding attention toward stimulus or far away from it controls the amount of information being processed that threatens the individual, and facilitates motivating cognitive, behavioral, emotive, and psychological stimulation or hinders them. The result may also be explained by what Gaweda, Prochwicz and Cella (2015) said that the prevalence of psychotic experiences such as hallucinations and delusions are not limited to psychotic patients, but can be observed in society as a whole as well. In the same respect, Van Os and his colleagues (2009) confirmed that 8% of the society has psychotic experiences; nevertheless, these experiences do not associate with any psychiatric disturbances.

Results showed statistical differences in cognitive biases among Qassim University students attributed to their majors. The relation of these majors with implementation and practice explain this result; this entails to focus on the stimulus correlated with learning. Students study by sequencing clear specific steps to reach facts, this process forms behavior, it requires focus and follow up of a certain stimulus, therefore this helps the student to take decisions based on logic rather than supposition and probability and avoid cognitive bias. But in

humanitarian majors the students encounter problems by being unable to organize perceptions or integrate capabilities, this may be a direct cause in the learning problems students encounter because they rely in humanitarian majors on memorizing and recalling which may lead to information interference, thinking and possibilities and cause distortion of perceptions, irrational interpretations or irrationality. (Van der Gaag et al., 2013)

Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the effect of the academic achievement level was found. Cognitive biases level among the low academic achievers was higher compared with the high academic achievers. This result reveals the role of cognitive bias in maladjustment of the student and its affect in many aspects of the characteristic including the academic domain. Low academic achievers may use ineffective adjustment strategies; they are more vulnerable to commit thinking mistakes and cognitive biases in collecting information and accordingly jump to conclusions without depending on adequate logical evidence. These students thinking may be inflexible, or tend to think improperly and tend to reduce coincidence probability and maximize the causality probability between things and events.

Significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the interaction between major and academic achievement level in jumping to conclusions, social cognition problems, and safety behaviors, in favor of humanitarian majors were found. Perhaps the most prominent result in this study is cognitive biases differences attributed to the academic achievement level, the differences were in favor of low achievers.

The results of this study disagreed with Jaber and Abed Al-Ameer (2017), they said that cognitive biases were insignificant, and the major's influence on cognitive differences was insignificant. On the other hand, it agreed with the results of Al-Hammouri (2017) who found a moderate level of cognitive biases and its domains. He found that low academic achievers have higher levels of cognitive bias compared with high achievers. The results also agreed with the results Mahmoud and Al-Lami (2020) study; they found that kindergarten teacher's students have cognitive bias.

The current study genuineness and goals renders it as a cornerstone to the psychological literature of the Saudi community. It may participate in transferring the responsibility of learning to the learners themselves by training them to focus on certain stimulus rather than others, and therefore take logical decisions rather than supposition and probability, it helps them to avoid cognitive biases thus use powers and abilities to enhance output and to makes the best possible investment of learning.

Conclusions

Based on the statistical analysis conducted, it was possible to determine the following;

- Qassim University students have a moderate level of cognitive biases.
- Students in humanitarian majors have more cognitive biases compared with students in scientific majors; this result is correlated with the practice and implementation methods of employed in studying in the scientific majors. Attention should be directed toward certain stimulus contrary to the focus on memorizing and recall in the humanitarian majors, which leads to information intersection and forgetting that increases the processes of intuition and guessing.
- Results showed significant differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) attributed to the academic achievement impact. Low academic achievers cognitive biases were higher than high academic achievers.

In light of the results the researcher recommends scholars to conduct more studies on the validity of the cognitive biases test on different types of participants and different ages; to implement the test on students in schools to reveal the extremist cases between them and find the correlation of cognitive biases with different mental disorders; and to examine the direct and indirect correlation of cognitive biases with the psychological characteristics such as the self-concept, metacognitive skills, or personality styles; to design training programs to prevent cognitive biases among the university students; and to reconsider curricula from early school stages to university and focus on logical inference abilities and effective strategies to reduce cognitive biases.

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